

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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A Fine Tuning Strategy to Improve Musical Source Separation Quality for Indian Carnatic Music

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Abstract

Abstract

The computational analysis of Carnatic music from audio remains a field of high research interest due to the genre’s rich melodic and rhythmic complexity. However, despite the availability of large multitrack collections such as *Saraga*, the live-recorded nature of this repertoire leads to a scarcity of truly clean instrument and vocal stems, posing significant challenges for both musicological and technological studies. State-of-the-art music source separation (MSS) models perform poorly on Carnatic music due to a pronounced domain mismatch with their training data.

This work proposes a **fine-tuning strategy** for improving separation of *vocals*, *mridangam*, and *violin plus tanpura* stems in Carnatic music. The approach uses a *Sparse Compression U-Net (SCNet)* pretrained on *MusDB18*, extended with a curated training set combining clean Carnatic multitrack recordings and out-of-domain data. To further reduce the domain gap, three data augmentations are introduced: (i) **violin sampling augmentation**, (ii) **microphone-bleeding simulation**, and (iii) **room impulse response convolution**.

The proposed model achieves substantial SDR improvements over the baselines on a clean Carnatic benchmark derived from the *Sanidha* dataset, and a perceptual evaluation on *Saraga* confirms significant quality gains on all 3 separated sources. On the benchmark, the best configuration outperforms all baselines by a large margin in SDR, while training in under two days on a single *40 GB GPU* - making it considerably less resource-exhaustive than many similar deep learning-based MSS domain adaptation methods.

All pretrained models, code, a cleaned version of the *Saraga* dataset, and the *Sanidha* benchmark are released alongside this work.

Keywords: Musical Source Separation, Carnatic music

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Challenges in Carnatic Source Separation

Musical Source Separation (MSS) - the task of isolating individual source components from a musical mixture - has seen tremendous progress in recent years due to advances in deep learning. Machine-cleaned stems are now often indistinguishable from original studio recordings. However, current MSS systems are typically trained in a supervised fashion, requiring multi-track datasets where each instrument is recorded separately. Such datasets are expensive to produce due to their studio-recorded nature and are often restricted by copyright.

Consequently, the aforementioned advances in MSS are largely confined to the limited data domain of Western, studio-recorded pop and rock music with standard instrumentation. Publicly available datasets such as *MUSDB18* [1] and *MoisesDB* [2], serving both as training sets and benchmarks for model evaluation, have played a key role within improving the MSS quality in this domain.

Carnatic music, a form of South Indian classical music, poses new challenges for MSS research. State-of-the-art models like *Hybrid Demucs* [3] struggle with its instrumentation, timbres, and unique musical structure. For instance, the **Mridangam** - a pitched, complexly tuned drum that provides the rhythmic foundation in Carnatic music - is often improperly separated: harmonic components are mistak-

Figure 1: A Carnatic performance[4]. Instruments (left to right): Mridangam, Kanjira (check), Vocalist, Tanpura, Violin

only removed, resulting in sharper transients and reduced decay compared to the original sound. Melodic instruments in Carnatic music are traditionally performed in a *gāyaki* (singing-style) manner. The violin, for example, closely mimics the phrasing and melodic improvisation of the vocalist. This leads to substantial frequency overlap between voice and violin, causing cross-contamination in separated stems: residual violin components in the voice stem, and vice versa. Additionally, Carnatic music is typically recorded live during concerts. As a result, the audio contains room reverb, ambient noise, and a less clean and polished mix, further complicating separation with models trained on studio-recorded datasets. These mismatches in data domain, instrumentation, and recording context present persistent challenges to existing MSS models. Overcoming these limitations unlocks possibilities for computational musicological and technological tasks working directly on the carnatic mixture.

1.2 Motivation and Objectives

1.2.1 Carnatic Musicology

Carnatic music is a widespread classical art music genre, prevalent in South India and Sri Lanka. Alongside Hindustani music from North India, it constitutes what is commonly referred to as **Indian classical** or **Indian art music**. Both traditions are performance-based and heterophonic, characterised by a principal melodic

line rendered by a lead performer, and place strong emphasis on improvisation. While vocal performance is essential to both traditions, it is particularly central in Carnatic music. Instrumental performance is also integral; however, a key stylistic distinction lies in the aesthetic goals of the instrumentalists: in Carnatic music, they typically aim to emulate vocal renditions, whereas Hindustani instrumental music has developed more independently from its vocal roots.[5]

Indian classical music is widely regarded as one of the most complex musical systems in the world, with a very highly developed melodic and rhythmic structure[6]. It traces its origins to the Vedic period (c. 1200-900 BCE), and while core textual elements remain preserved,[7] indian classical music itself is living and continually evolving and developing through contemporary interpretation and performance.[6] The melodic and rhythmic analysis of Carnatic music is of significant interest to computational and musicological research due to the mutual existence of pre-defined elements (rāgas) and improvisation:

The Structural Elements of Carnatic Music

Rāgas are the primary melodic frameworks in Carnatic Music[8]. A rāga in Carnatic music can be characterised by a set of **distinctive motifs**[9], formed by the inflected movement of **svaras**. Svaras are the indian classical music equivalent to the solfeg (*do-re-mi-fa-sol?*) - a definite pitch which relates to and gets its identity from the fixed tonic, called **ṣaḍja** [10]. Svaras can be further shaped through **gamakas** - continuous pitch modulations that connect melodic phrases into expressive wholes.[11] Gamakas are not merely ornamental; they carry grammatical and structural significance and are selected intuitively by the performers.

While these categories - rāga, motif, svara, gamaka - can be loosely compared to Western music-structural concepts such as scales, note-sheets, motives, or expressive notation, they extend beyond structural analogies. The authors of [10] emphasize that:

“While various phrases within a rāga can be studied and understood independently for theoretical analysis, the rāga exists as a whole. A rāga is not static. Every

composition and every performance of the rāga is part of its evolution.”

The actual structure of carnatic music - the interpretation of the raga by a carnatic ensemble - lies in the **performance**, making audio analysis essential for musicological research. Consequently, many studies in computational ethnomusicology focus on tasks such as melodic pattern recognition and automatic rāga detection from audio.[12]

Improved source separation directly enhances such tasks by allowing researchers to work on isolated stems rather than noisy, reverberant mixtures. This also benefits a broad audience with millions of listeners worldwide who profits from improved melodic or raga identification systems through music-technological application like music recommendation and personalized retrieval systems tailored to Carnatic music.[13]

Additionally, the availability of the large and well-annotated **Saraga AV** dataset[14] has led to substantial advances in data-driven musicological research on Carnatic music. The open, multi-modal dataset of over 60 hours of Carnatic performance videos, aligned with multi-stem audio, expert annotations, and rich metadata has become an essential resource for work in computational musicology, melodic analysis, and audio-visual musical source separation for carnatic music and beyond.

However, due to its live-recorded nature, Saraga suffers from **source bleeding**, where the individual stems contain signal leakage from other instruments (see Chapter 2.2). Preceding research proved the difficulties of evaluating MSS systems with common metrics like the *Source-To-Distortion Ratio*, if the models train on data with bleeding. Residuals in the separated stems don't get penalized correctly, as the references contain residuals themselves.

In the context of **Audio-Visual Musical Source Separation(AV-MSS)**, models are trained to condition on time-synchronized video features in addition to the audio mixture. Saraga AV is currently the largest publicly available multi-stem AV dataset for this purpose, but its effectiveness is limited by the same source-bleeding problem. Audiovisual conditioning often yields only marginal improvements that can hardly

be detected with automatic evaluation metrics like SDR and leakage containing groundtruths.

A machine-cleaned version of the Saraga dataset with stems cleaned using a reliable MSS system would offer substantial value to multiple research threads. The bleeding-free version of the dataset not only simplifies melodic analysis or audio-visual source separation tasks, but also makes Saraga a dataset that can easily be used in combination with other source separation datasets like MUSDB18 or MoisesDB - an important step to include more non-western as well as musicological precious data into the canon of widely used source separation datasets.

1.2.2 Objectives

To address the challenges identified above, this thesis aims to **improve music source separation quality** for Carnatic music by pursuing the following objectives:

- Develop a multi-stem Carnatic **benchmark** to compare models and evaluate the improvement
- Propose a domain-adaptation **finetuning strategy** to improve over baseline models
 - Introduce **data augmentation techniques** to bridge the gap between studio-recorded training data and the often live-recorded nature of real Carnatic performances.
 - Leverage pre-trained MSS models to reduce the ecological impact compared to training *state-of-the-art* models from scratch
- Evaluate the performance of all converged models on the benchmark and compare results with the strongest available open-source MSS systems.
- Apply the best-performing model to **clean Saraga AV dataset**.
- Release the **model weights** and **codebase**, including data augmentation methods, to support reproducibility.

Figure 2: A spectral analysis of the Mridangam strokes conducted by [15].

- Provide a **bleeding-reduced** version of the Saraga AV dataset to support future research in Carnatic musicology and audiovisual source separation.

1.2.3 Carnatic Instrumentation

The remainder of this chapter provides a brief introduction to Carnatic instrumentation. Figure 6 depicts a Carnatic concert from the Saraga Audiovisual dataset. In the performance, a *violin* follows the improvised vocal line, while a *mridangam* player provides rhythmic accompaniment.

Carnatic instruments can be broadly categorized into three groups: melodic instruments, rhythmic instruments, and drones. Melodic instruments include the *violin* and the *Saraswati Veena*. Drum instruments such as the *Mridangam* and *Ghatam* provide rhythm and percussive textures. Finally, drone instruments like the *Tanpura* create a *wall-of-sound* drone that typically remains in the background.

Mridangam

The mridangam is the primary percussion instrument, the main instrument used in Carnatic music concerts to keep the performance in a rhythmic pattern[4]. It is mentioned in historical manuscripts as far back as 200 B.C. and has gradually

developed into the most prominent percussion instrument played in South Indian classical music.[15]. The mridangam is a double-headed drum, see Figure 1.3(a). It is played using several different strokes on the treble (right) and bass (left) membrane. Different finger positions and methods of striking the drumheads produce a variety of tones, with some strokes producing harmonic sounds with a recognizable pitch, and some producing tonic-independent sounds[16]. These *strokes*, many of which got names over time, create a vocabulary of different sound-types. The authors of [15] categorize these strokes into 3 classes:

- Ringing string-like tones played on the treble membrane
 - *Dhin, Cha or Bheem*
- Flat, closed, crisp sounds.
 - *Thi, Ta and Num*
- Resonant strokes played on the bass membrane
 - *Thom*

Figure 2 shows spectrogram representations of the different stroke types introduced above. The presence of horizontal lines in the spectrograms indicates the harmonic-rich nature of mridangam decays. In particular, the strokes *Bheem*, *Cha*, and *Dhin* - played on the treble side of the mridangam - exhibit long, sustained harmonic fade-outs. This stands in contrast to classic western drum kits, whose percussive elements typically lack discernible harmonics in their spectral representations.

Tanpura

Tanpura is a multi-stringed and fretless accompanying drone instrument extensively used in classical music in India. Instrumentalists create an underlying drone background sound by plucking the Tanpura by finger. Jitter, shimmer and complexity perturbations are found also in tanpura signals[17]. Figure 1.3(b) shows a photo of a Tanpura.

Figure 3: The 3 carnatic instruments separated in this work

Violin

Violin-like string instruments have been used in Indian classical music, before the western violin got introduced in India around the 18th century. Carnatic musicians play western violins with different posture and tuning - generally much lower and with different intervals. For a tonic C the four strings would be tuned to $C^3 - G^3 - C^4 - G^4$. The instrument furthermore is played in *gāyaki* style (see Section 1.2.1), usually follows the vocalists improvisation. In contrast to western violin, it follows a different scale with smaller intervals than the semitone. The violin also plays *Gamakas* - analog to vibrato or glissando in western music. Figure 1.3(c) illustrates that the Carnatic violin is built identical to its Western counterpart.

1.3 Structure of the Report

This report is structured as follows:

The **state-of-the-art** (Chapter 2) situates this work within prior research I accompanied at the *MTG - Music Technology Group, Barcelona* - on Carnatic source separation and bleeding-aware source separation. Furthermore, important developments in both areas are discussed, along with related works on source separation domain adaptation and a presentation of the neural networks used in this project.

The **methodology** (Chapter 3) presents the proposed fine-tuning strategy. First, the data-domain mismatch between the Carnatic domain and Western pop/rock

music - represented by MUSDB18 - is analyzed. Next, I introduce a fine-tuning dataset and data augmentations tailored specifically to bridge these domain gaps.

The **experimental setup** (Chapter 3.3) describes the four different configurations of the proposed models, the baselines and the evaluation procedure of the experiments.

Finally, **results**, Chapter 4, presents the evaluation results followed by **conclusion and discussion** (Chapter 5) where they are summarized and critically discussed.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

This chapter provides an overview of the current state of research in Carnatic source separation by:

- Surveying relevant literature and highlighting the link to research in the field of **bleeding source separation** due to the carnatic MSS datasets available
- Introducing research works on similar **source-separation domain adaptation** problems
- Presenting the **architectural developments** in source separation neural networks with a focus on models used within this work
- Reviewing available **datasets** for Carnatic MSS and related collections that serve as the foundation for this thesis

2.1 Carnatic Music Source Separation

Several studies have noted that publicly available pre-trained source separation models often exhibit poor generalization to Carnatic music. [19, 20, 21, 22]. Due to the limited availability of source-leakage free carnatic multistem audios, most literature as well as my own preceding research focuses on leveraging the bleeding-containing

Figure 4: Microphone bleeding[24]

saraga stems to improve performance of carnatic source separation systems. Even if these systems didn't yet outperform baselines like Hybrid Transformer Demucs [23], trained on clean out-of-domain data, significant improvements over baselines trained solely on the saraga bleeding stems have been made. These results suggest that source separation models are capable of deriving single-source information from training data that contains inter-source bleeding. This indicates that, in data domains where microphone leakage is common, bleeding-aware approaches are likely to outperform models that do not explicitly account for such interference in the future.

The following chapter introduces microphone-bleeding and different bleeding-aware and unaware approaches for carnatic MSS.

2.2 Microphone Bleeding

Microphone bleeding or **Microphone leakage** describes a phenomena of live multi-microphone recordings with multiple instruments/sound sources[24]. Figure 4 provides a simplified illustration of microphone bleeding.

In a recording scenario with N sound sources $s_n(k)$ in a reverberant environment, M microphones capture signals denoted as $x_m(k)$. Let $h_{mn}(k)$ represent the room

impulse response modeling the acoustic path from source n to microphone m . Assuming that each microphone is primarily intended to capture a single target source, the signal at microphone m can be expressed as:

$$x_m(k) = s_m(k) * h_{mm}(k) + \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq m}}^M s_n(k) * h_{mn}(k)$$

Then, the direct source, the convolution of the target source $s_m(k)$ with its direct path $h_{mm}(k)$ is defined via the first part of the equation:

$$\hat{s}_m(k) = s_m(k) * h_{mm}(k)$$

The second term, accounting for the contributions from all other sources due to room reflections and cross-talk, defines the bleeding component:

$$u_m(k) = \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq m}}^M s_n(k) * h_{mn}(k)$$

Neural network based MSS systems commonly minimize reconstruction losses like *L1-distance* or *mean-square-error* in a supervised training way requiring stem-data as groundtruths. If stems contain leakage, the model therefore learns to average a bleeding components $\hat{u}_m(k)$, derived from all the bleeding components of the target sources in the dataset.

Additionally, evaluation of the training success becomes increasingly challenging with the bleeding level of the dataset. Standard MSS evaluation metrics such as *SDR* (see Section 3.4.1) and *ISR* are designed to assess the overall signal quality and the level of interference between stems. However, these metrics can become misleading in bleeding scenarios. For example, if the target source is almost silent during a specific interval in the benchmark, the separation output may still contain a residual mixture signal due to learned bleeding patterns. As a result, metrics like SDR and ISR may yield highly negative scores, as they interpret the presence

of any residual energy as distortion or interference, despite the model reproducing the typical leakage observed during training. The following paragraphs summarizes developments in bleeding-aware approaches for Carnatic MSS that rethink training objectives to tackle the aforementioned challenges.

2.2.1 Bleeding Aware Source Separation

Recent work by Plaja et al. [22] introduces *bleeding-aware* techniques to improve source separation performance for Carnatic singing voice using diffusion based approaches. However, these approaches still face two key limitations: the overall separation quality does not yet match state-of-the-art results in the broader literature, and current efforts focus exclusively on separating the singing voice, neglecting other important sources.

In a following paper *Disentangling Overlapping Sources: Improving Vocal and Violin Source Separation in Carnatic Music* [25], written by A. Shankar, myself, G. Plaja and M. Rocamora, we proposed a bleeding-aware two-stage training procedure targeting both voice and violin stems. This approach draws inspiration from advances in speech denoising and enhancement, where learned loss functions that approximate perceptual metrics - such as *PESQ* or *STOI* - have been shown to improve separation quality [26, 27].

For instance, Wuxuan et al. [28] train a dense convolutional neural network to predict *PESQ* and *STOI* scores, both of which are meant to correlate with the perceived cleanness of speech signals. During training, a random *PESQ* target value y_{pesq} is sampled, and noise x_{noise} is scaled and added to a clean speech signal x_{speech} such that:

$$y_{\text{pesq}} = \text{PESQ}(x_{\text{speech}}, x_{\text{speech}} + s \cdot x_{\text{noise}})$$

The model then learns to map the noisy input $x_{\text{speech}} + s \cdot x_{\text{noise}}$ to the target perceptual score y_{pesq} .

In [25], we adapted this framework to the bleeding problem by simulating artificial bleed for Carnatic voice and violin stems. The leakage component is modeled following an algorithm introduced in the **SDX Bleeding Challenge 2023** [29]. The provided benchmark and training dataset are generated via simulated inter-source leakage on the multi-stem sources from MUSDB18.

The authors simulated bleeding following these assumptions:

- The amount of bleeding in a recording is usually low
 - Authors define the bleeding level via source separation evaluation, aiming for a difference of 1db in SDR when models train on the bleeding containing data, compared to the same model, trained on clean MUSDB18
- Every single file contains bleeding
- Every stem bleeds into every other stem in the same song
- The bleeding component of one stem for another stem is obtained by:
 - Apply gain reduction, random between **-7db** and **-12db**
 - Filter: Choose Band or Lowpass filter with **p=0.5**
 - Order: between **3** and **10**
 - Lowpass: Cutoff frequency between **900** and **9000Hz**
 - Bandpass: Low cutoff between **200** and **600Hz**, high cutoff between **8** and **10** kHz

All values are sampled from uniform distributions. The ranges were obtained empirically, compromising between bleeding realism and the desired goal of -1db in SDR[29].

Following this procedure, we implemented a *PyTorch*[30] dataloader that generates synthetic bleeding mixtures from clean Carnatic multi-stem studio recordings during each training step. The clean source material is sampled from the CMC dataset (see

Section 2.6.4). Before training, a target stem is selected - either *vocal* or *violin* - while the remaining stems (*mridangam left*, *mridangam right*, and *tanpura*) are treated as sources of leakage, following the approach described above.

A bleeding level $b \in [0, 1]$ is randomly sampled for each example. Both the target stem and the combined bleeding stems are loudness-normalized. The final mixture is then computed as:

$$x_{\text{train}} = (1 - b) \cdot x_{\text{target}} + b \cdot x_{\text{bleed}}$$

Note that x_{target} is either x_{vocal} or x_{violin} while x_{bleed} is a filtered and gain reduced sum of all the remaining sources of the CMC dataset.

A convolutional neural network, structurally identical to the discriminator used in MelGAN [31], is trained to learn the mapping from the input x_{train} to the bleeding level b .

We then pre-train a U-Net architecture [32] on the Saraga dataset for 300,000 iterations, minimizing *L1 distance* computed against bleeding-containing targets. Through this process, the model learns to suppress background instrumentation to match the average bleeding level present in the Saraga recordings.

In the second stage, we fine-tune the pre-trained model by replacing the L1 loss with the learned bleeding estimator introduced earlier.

During the finetuning, the model learns to lower the bleeding residuals significantly. The pre-training was performed on approximately 60 hours of Saraga data, while fine-tuning required only 300 iterations on a subset of 2 hours of Saraga. This suggests that the model already learns an internal representation of isolated, bleeding-free source components during pre-training. However, the discriminator loss introduced occasionally audible artifacts, steadily increasing during the finetuning stage. Due to the resulting limitation in effective duration of this second training phase the final separation quality does not yet match that of state-of-the-art systems trained

on clean datasets such as MUSDB18, when evaluated on clean Carnatic recordings. Despite current limitations, the observed improvements underscore the potential of bleeding-aware methods in carnatic source separation research.

2.3 Bleeding Unaware Source Separation

The above mentioned **Sound Demixing Challenge 2023** introduced a new benchmark and leaderboard specifically targeting bleeding source separation, providing participants with a dataset of pop songs augmented with artificially simulated leakage [29]. The test set was generated using the same bleeding simulation procedure as the training set described in 2.2.1, but sampled songs from the MoisesDB dataset [2].

The top-performing submission in the challenge employed a loss truncation strategy, wherein only time segments with low loss values contributed to the optimization process [33]. This approach yielded an improvement of approximately 1 dB over the baseline. However, the system still struggled to effectively mitigate bleeding artifacts. Notably, this method is not a bleeding-aware training strategy; it succeeds in the SDX context because the simulated leakage is uniformly distributed across sources and time segments. In opposite, the bleeding components of real world datasets, like Saraga, are not randomly distributed in volume per source, but follow patterns, depending on the stage and recording setup. The Mridangam, for example, often bleeds more due to higher loudness of the transients. The vocal microphone, on the other hand, typically records more bleeding than the mridangam microphones, due to it's position in the center of the stage, pointing towards the ensemble. As a result, loss-masking techniques may lead to the systematic underrepresentation of important bleeding cases during training in the context of carnatic music.

In our prior work [25], we also explored a **bleeding-unaware** approach. We trained a two-stem *Kuielab MDX model* [32] to perform vocal and violin separation on the Saraga dataset, using again the L_1 loss against bleeding-containing targets. The model architecture comprises two independent *TFC-TDF U-Nets* [34], one for each source and without shared parameters. A mixer module, implemented as a single

dense layer, receives both source estimates and the original mixture as input. The model was trained for 300,000 iterations.

Qualitatively, the resulting separations exhibited reduced bleeding in the violin track. However, this approach still falls short in overall quality when compared to state-of-the-art models such as the Hybrid Transformer Demucs. Furthermore, the bleeding reduction appears to rely on the model’s internal optimization dynamics - i.e., minimizing the target loss by implicitly suppressing bleeding content. Due to the black-box nature of deep learning models, this behavior is difficult to analyze, reproduce, or adapt to other datasets or source types.

2.4 Data-Domain Adaptation Challenges in Music Source Separation

The master’s thesis *Vocal Source Separation for Carnatic Music* [35] addresses a similar data-domain adaptation problem. In this work, A. Shankar collects a small dataset of Carnatic vocal performances and trains two versions of a *Spleeter* [36] source separation model: one from scratch on the collected dataset and another by fine-tuning a pre-trained model originally trained on MUSDB18. The fine-tuned model significantly outperforms the version trained solely on Carnatic data. This finding supports the notion that leveraging pre-trained models and incorporating out-of-domain datasets - such as MUSDB18 - can not only reduce training time and resource exhaustion, but also improve separation performance in domain-specific tasks.

A similar fine-tuning strategy is employed by Chen [37], who adapts a large state-of-the-art model to the domain of Jingju (Chinese opera). A dedicated dataset is first collected, then the author fine-tunes a sparse HTDemucs model - the same model used as a baseline in this thesis - on the Jingju data.

Both of these studies follow comparable approaches to address domain shift in music source separation, with a strong emphasis on original data collection. In contrast, this work benefits from the timely availability of several domain-relevant datasets,

Figure 5: An example source separation U-Net from the paper: *Wave-U-Net: A Multi-Scale Neural Network for End-to-End Audio Source Separation* [38].

including the CMC dataset, Saraga AV, and Sanidha. These resources became available during the development of this thesis 2024 till 2025, eliminating the need for extensive new data collection.

As a result, this work focuses primarily on dataset composition, data-domain analysis, and training strategies - including data augmentation and fine-tuning techniques. Additionally, the recent release of SCNet provided a lightweight yet powerful source separation architecture, capable of converging rapidly and efficiently. Unlike the approach proposed by Chen, which required 8 *NVIDIA V100 GPUs* for fine-tuning, SCNet enables faster experimentation and comparison across different configurations.

2.5 U-Nets for Musical Source Separation

In recent years, the quality of music source separation has improved significantly, largely due to advances in neural network architectures. One of the earliest successful

deep learning model for this task was proposed by Lin et al. [39], who introduced a U-Net architecture for singing voice separation. Since then, many state-of-the-art models have followed this general design principle, with various modifications.

The U-Net architecture is composed of four main components, inspired by encoder-decoder networks:

- **Encoder:** A series of downsampling blocks, reducing the temporal or time-frequency resolution of the input representation while increasing the number of feature channels. This enables the model to extract progressively more abstract representations of the mixture. These blocks typically consist of *convolutional layers*, *pooling* operations, and optional *normalization* layers.
- **Bottleneck:** Situated between the encoder and decoder, the bottleneck operates on the deepest layer, receiving the most compressed representation of the input. It is often augmented with a temporal modeling component, such as a *Transformer* [3], *bidirectional LSTM* [40], or *TFC module* [41]. These *recurrent neural networks* contain some kind of memory, allowing the model to capture long-range temporal dependencies that are difficult to model using purely sequential operations.
- **Decoder:** The decoder gradually reconstructs the representation of the target source from the bottleneck output, typically mirroring the encoder’s structure. The upsampling blocks of the decoder often feature *(de)convolution layers*, *upsampling layers* and *normalizations*.
- **Skip Connections:** The defining feature of a U-Net, distinguishing it from classical encoder networks, are the skip connections, transferring feature maps from encoder layers to corresponding decoder layers, usually after each downsampling and upsampling step. These connections help preserve high-resolution and temporal detail, and reduce the burden on the bottleneck to carry all relevant information to reconstruct the audio sources. Implementations of skip connections vary in complexity, ranging from simple concatenations [38] to fusion layers filtering and compressing information with *Gated Linear Units* [42].

Figure 5 shows an early U-Net model for source separation. In this example, the bottleneck is implemented as a simple convolutional layer, lacking the recurrent modeling components commonly found in modern architectures.

2.5.1 (Hybrid) (Transformer) Demucs

The various iterations of the *Demucs*[40] architecture have introduced several innovations to the U-Net framework. Early source separation U-Nets operated either in the time-frequency (spectrogram) domain or directly on the waveform. In theory, both domains should offer equivalent information, since a spectrogram is simply a linear transformation of the waveform. However, in practice under limited training data availability, each approach exhibits distinct characteristics and limitations.

Spectrogram-based methods often struggle to accurately reconstruct sharp high-frequency content and percussive elements such as drums [3]. On the other hand, waveform-based methods tend to produce fewer phase-related artifacts but are known to be more sensitive to variations in the training data. For instance, Su et al. [43] report that waveform-based models generalize poorly to unseen noise types and reverberant conditions. Additionally, spectrogram-based models generally exhibit faster convergence during training compared to their waveform-based counterparts [44].

To leverage the strengths of both domains, the *Hybrid Demucs* architecture incorporates two branches that process spectrogram and waveform representations. Building on this, the *Hybrid Transformer Demucs* (*HTDemucs*) [23] integrates a dual-branch Transformer module as the bottleneck to enhance temporal modeling.

Given the data requirements of Transformer architectures, the authors additionally fine-tune the model on 800 extra songs. This enhanced version, referred to as *HTDemucs_{ft}*, currently represents the state of the art in open-source music source separation. However, its large model size and substantial data requirements make it resource-intensive and challenging to train from scratch. In this work, *HTDemucs_{ft}* is used as a benchmark for evaluating separation performance.

2.5.2 SCNet

The work *SCNet: Sparse Compression Network for Music Source Separation* [42] introduces a novel approach to spectrogram-based source separation U-Nets, with a particular emphasis on training time and stability. Unlike hybrid models, SCNet operates entirely in the spectrogram domain.

A key architectural innovation is the use of *sparse compression* blocks in the encoder. These blocks divide the input spectrogram into multiple subbands and apply varying compression rates depending on the perceptual information density.

The bottleneck consists of a modified *Bandsplit-RNN module* [45], which processes each subband individually to capture temporal dependencies. The decoder mirrors the encoder’s structure with *sparse decompression* blocks. Information from the encoder is passed to the decoder via skip connections, implemented using *fusion layers*, which combine summation operations with *Gated Linear Units* [46] for selective information flow.

The SCNet serves both as a baseline as well as the pre-trained model for the finetuning experiments in this work. While the paper also introduces a large configuration with more parameters and just slightly better results on the MusDB18 benchmark, this work focuses on the lightweight version to reduce training resources.

RMSE-Loss

The SCNet operates entirely in the frequency domain. The authors therefore avoid waveform-based losses that are widely used in MSS training objectives, and pick *root mean square error* as the loss function, operating directly on the complex spectrograms. The loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \sqrt{(r - \hat{r})^2 + (i - \hat{i})^2}$$

where r and i denote the real and imaginary parts of the predicted spectrogram, and \hat{r} , \hat{i} represent the corresponding components of the ground truth.

Figure 6: A Carnatic concert from the Saraga Audiovisual dataset. Instrumentation: Mridangam (left), Violin (right), Vocalist (center)

2.6 Datasets

In the following section, all datasets used within this project are presented:

2.6.1 Saraga

The Saraga-Audiovisual dataset [14] is the largest open-access, multistem collection of Carnatic music, comprising 64.8 hours of concert recordings. It consists exclusively of live Carnatic performances captured with multiple microphones on stage. Compared to the original Saraga dataset [47], the number of artists and rāgas has approximately doubled, while the overall duration and number of recordings remain comparable [14]. Moreover, Saraga reflects the stylistic diversity, musical beauty, and nuanced performance practices of Carnatic music. This stands in contrast to other widely used open musical source separation datasets such as MUSDB18, which primarily feature studio-produced tracks with a commercial or advertisement-oriented sound.

2.6.2 MUSDB18

MUSDB18 [1] is the most widely used MSS dataset. The stems include: **Vocal**, **Drums**, **Other** and **Bass**. Other features many kinds of melodic instruments and electronic sounds. Bass includes baselines, played by bass-guitars and sub-frequency

synthesizers.

2.6.3 Sanidha

The Sanidha dataset [48] is a multimodal, audiovisual, multistem Carnatic music collection with little to no leakage between sources. It contains recordings of five Carnatic concerts performed at the *School of Music, Georgia Institute of Technology (USA)*, featuring fifteen professional Carnatic musicians from Atlanta: three male vocalists, two female vocalists, four violinists, and six percussionists. The performances were captured in four soundproof rooms equipped with acoustic curtains, significantly reducing room reverberation. For synchronization purposes, each performer received a personalized monitor mix consisting of the other performers' microphones, combined with an artificial tanpura drone.

In the initial recording sessions, some performers required higher monitoring levels, which led to slight leakage from the headphones into their microphones. This issue was addressed in later sessions by switching to in-ear monitoring. As a result, concerts 2 and 3 are completely free from leakage, whereas the remaining three concerts exhibit minor bleed, especially on the vocalist tracks in the form of a metronome-like click sound.

2.6.4 Carnatic Multi-stem Clean (CMC)

The Carnatic **Multi-stem Clean (CMC)** dataset is a private collection of 58 multistem Carnatic music recordings, totaling approximately 5 hours of audio. Each recording includes one or two lead vocals, violin, mridangam, and tanpura, with some concerts also featuring tāla and veena. The dataset was provided by *Shaale*, a Bangalore-based company specializing in Indian art music education. It was originally recorded for educational purposes, enabling Carnatic musicians to practice alongside a complete ensemble. Notably, each instrument was captured in acoustic isolation, ensuring that no bleed occurs between tracks.

Figure 1 compares the stems included in the four presented MSS datasets.

2.6.5 Bach Violin Dataset

The Bach Violin Dataset [49] contains high-quality public recordings of Johann Sebastian Bach’s sonatas and partitas for solo violin (*BWV 1001–1006*). It comprises 6.5 hours of performances by 17 professional violinists, recorded in a variety of sessions. In addition to the audio, the dataset provides reference scores and estimated alignments between the recordings and the corresponding scores, enabling score-informed processing and analysis. The dataset is bleeding and noise free.

2.6.6 Deep Noise Suppression Dataset (DNS)

The DNS Challenge [50] is an annual competition that provides benchmarks and datasets for various speech enhancement tasks. It has been hosted at *INTERSPEECH 2020*, *ICASSP 2021*, *INTERSPEECH 2021*, *ICASSP 2022*, and *ICASSP 2023*. In the 2022 edition, the organizers released an additional curated dataset comprising 48 real and approximately 60,000 simulated room impulse responses (RIRs) to support research on joint speech denoising and dereverberation [51]. The RIRs were sourced from the *OpenSLR26* and *OpenSLR28* datasets [52] without further modification or specification.

Chapter 3

A Finetuning Strategy - Methodology

Previous research around Carnatic musical source separation shows that, at the time of this work, MSS models trained solely on 8 hours of the out-of-domain, leakage-free dataset MUSDB18 outperform models trained in a bleeding-aware manner on more than 60 hours of in-domain Carnatic data from the Saraga-AV dataset (see Section 2.2.1).

Furthermore, related research on MSS domain adaptation highlights the superiority of fine-tuning pre-trained models with in-domain data over training from scratch using only in-domain data (see Section 2.4).

Based on these findings, this work proposes a strategy for curating datasets and designing data augmentations to fine-tune a pre-trained SCNet using leakage-free data. First, the domain characteristics of Carnatic music are analysed, with emphasis on instrumentation, genre-specific differences compared to Western pop and rock, and recording/performance conditions. Next, I present a new dataset that draws from both out-of-domain and in-domain sources to represent the Carnatic music domain as comprehensively as possible. Additionally, multiple data augmentation techniques are introduced to further bridge the gap between data domains. Finally, a dedicated test set is proposed as a benchmark for evaluating separation quality

Table 1: Correlating stems per dataset.

Dataset	Vocals	Drums	Other	Bass	Unused
Saraga	Vocals	Mridangam L/R	Violin	–	Ghatam; Veena
MUSDB18	Vocals	Drums	Other	Bass	–
CMC	Vocals	Mridangam	Tanpura; Violin	–	Taala; Veena
Sanidha	Vocals Vocals 1+2	Mridangam L/R	Violin 1-2; Tanpura	–	Ghatam Far; Ghatam Close

using standard MSS metrics as well as a perceptual test.

3.1 Data Domain Investigation: Carnatic Music vs. Western Pop and Rock

To curate a fine-tuning dataset that accurately represents the Carnatic music domain and its specific challenges for MSS, this chapter examines the musicological characteristics of Carnatic music (see Section 1.2.1) in relation to the available datasets (see Section 2.6). The goal is to identify and analyse the data-domain gap between Carnatic music and the MUSDB18 dataset, with a particular focus on MSS performance in the Carnatic context.

The following aspects are investigated:

- Instrumentation characteristics and their domain-specific MSS challenges
- Genre-specific differences and their MSS-related implications
- MSS challenges arising from the live-recorded nature of the performances

3.1.1 Instrumentation Differences and Challenges in Separating Carnatic Music with Out-of-Domain MSS Models

As described in Section 1.2.3, Carnatic music features a partly distinctive set of instruments, beyond the violin not typically found in Western popular music. In

preliminary experiments, I applied pre-trained MSS models - Hybrid Transformer Demucs (HTDemucs) and SCNet - both trained on MUSDB18, to separate Carnatic music recordings.

MUSDB18 consists of four stems for all tracks: *vocals*, *drums*, *bass*, and *other* (see Section 2.6.2). When applied to Carnatic music, models trained on that data tend to produce the following mapping:

- *Vocals* contain the lead vocal tracks.
- *Drums* contain *mridangam* and *ghatam*.
- *Other* contains *taala*, *tanpura*, *veena*, and *violin*.
- *Bass* typically contains silence or low-frequency residual noise, but no isolated instrument stems.

All separated stems contain residual bleed and, in some cases, omit portions of the target instruments. This work focuses on separating *vocals*, *violin*, *mridangam*, and *tanpura*, as these four instruments appear in every recording within the CMC, Sanidha, and Saraga datasets.¹

As discussed in Section 1.2.3, the mridangam produces both harmonic and noise-transient components. The spectral analysis (Figure 2) shows the long harmonic decays of strokes such as *Bheem*, *Cha*, and *Dhin*. When separating the mridangam with a model trained on MUSDB18, the ringing, string-like strokes often lose substantial portions of their long decay envelopes. Figure 7 illustrates how the harmonic components of these strokes are largely removed by HTDemucs_{ft}, despite preserving the initial transients.

3.1.2 Genre-Specific Challenges in Carnatic MSS

The *gāyaki* style in Carnatic music (see Section 1.2.1) creates a high melodic correlation and constant frequency overlap between the melodic instruments, particularly

¹Note: In the Saraga dataset, the *tanpura* is not provided as an isolated stem, but present as leakage in every recording.

Figure 7: Comparison of spectrograms: *Mridangam* audio separated from Sanidha concert 2 using an HTDemucs_{ft} model (right) and the clean reference (left). The HTDemucs_{ft} model preserves the transient components (vertical lines) but removes a significant portion of the harmonic decay (horizontal lines).

the violin and the vocal stems. In contrast, Western pop and rock arrangements rarely feature instrumental parts that mimic the lead vocal so closely. State-of-the-art MSS models such as SCNet and HTDemucs_{ft} operate entirely or partially in the frequency domain, using spectrograms as their primary input representation (see Sections 2.5.1 and 2.5.2). As a result, frequency-domain separation models trained primarily on Western data often struggle with Carnatic material, as the presence of violin in the same frequency bins as the vocal leads to significantly more residuals in the separated vocal stem and vice-versa.

Furthermore, Carnatic music utilises intervals that are smaller than the semitone, the smallest interval in Western music[12]. This might further complicate separation tasks for models trained exclusively on Western datasets with bigger and overall more discrete pitch scales.

3.1.3 Tailoring a Training Set and Benchmarks to Improve Carnatic MSS

Table 2 compares the four MSS datasets used in this work. Saraga, CMC, and Sanidha constitute the three Carnatic MSS datasets available at the time of writing.

Table 2: Overview of datasets used in this work.

Dataset	Length	Genre	Recording setup	Bleeding	Usage
Saraga	64.8 h	Carnatic	Live on stage	Yes	Evaluation
MUSDB18	10 h	Pop and Rock	Studio recorded	No	Training
CMC	8 h	Carnatic	Studio recorded	No	Training
Sanidha	4 h	Carnatic	Studio recorded	Partial	Evaluation

Figure 8: Stem mapping between MUSDB18 and the CMC dataset. MUSDB18 is standardized to four stems for every track. In CMC, additional tracks (*tāla*, *vīna*) are present in some concerts but are not used in this work.

Sanidha contains six concerts, of which concerts 2 and 3 are completely free of leakage and are therefore used as the primary evaluation benchmark for this work. MUSDB18 and CMC are leakage-free and thus suitable for training. I fine-tune models on CMC alone as well as on a combination of CMC and MUSDB18. In the latter case, Figure 8 shows the mapping between stems, as described in Section 3.1.1.

Of the 58 tracks in the CMC dataset, only 24 include violin. Furthermore, all violin-containing tracks are recorded with the same Carnatic ensemble - featuring a single violinist and a single recording setup. Since models often struggle with violin-vocal separation, I oversample these 24 tracks by including them twice in the training set, applying the data augmentations described in Section 3.2.1 to increase variety.

The Saraga dataset, with its stylistic diversity and real live-recorded performances, serves as the best available testing set for Carnatic music. Non-multistem Carnatic

recordings, such as publicly available concert recordings, are not suitable for the perceptual evaluation used in this work. State-of-the-art MSS models often remove parts of the target source during separation. To evaluate the completeness of the separated source, a comparative listening test with a reference is required. If the reference is the full mixture, assessing degradation becomes more difficult than when using the partially isolated, bleeding - containing stems of Saraga, where the target source is clearly in the foreground and perceptually distinct. Furthermore, this work aims to clean the Saraga AV dataset stems (see Chapter 1.2.2).

3.2 Data Augmentations

3.2.1 Aligning SCNet Data Augmentations with the Carnatic Data Domain

The original SCNet training procedure uses an augmentation pipeline consisting of four operations, each applied sequentially with its own probability. While these augmentations are designed to improve generalization, their effectiveness depends heavily on the match between the augmentation strategy and the target data domain. In this work, I propose a modified pipeline that retains three of the original augmentations and introduces three new ones specifically tailored to the characteristics of Carnatic music.

The authors of the SCNet propose the following augmentations:

Flip Channels - Swaps the left and right stereo channels of each source with a probability of $p = 0.5$.

Flip Sign - Inverts the phase of a source with a probability of $p = 0.5$.

Scale - Multiplies each source by a random scaling factor $s_{\text{scale}} \in [0.25, 1.25]$ with a probability of $p = 0.3$.

Remix - Randomly shuffles the same type of source across different mixtures within a batch.

The *Flip Channels*, *Flip Sign*, and *Scale* augmentations reduce overfitting and increase generalization capacities by varying model at every training step. Furthermore, the *Scale* augmentation is crucial for adapting to different mixdowns. For example, the CMC dataset contains only a single violin concert with a consistent loudness ratio between violin, vocal, and mridangam. Scaling these sources prepares the model for scenarios where the violin is mixed or played louder, or is more subdued in the background.

The *Remix* augmentation, originally proposed in the Demucs paper [40] and shown to improve separation quality and generalization in MUSDB18-trained models, is excluded from the modified SCNet pipeline. Preliminary experiments indicated that *Remix* degraded vocal and violin separation quality in the Carnatic context by disrupting melodic correlation. When violin stems are shuffled across mixtures, the number of temporally aligned samples with strong frequency overlap to the vocal is reduced. This negatively impacts performance of carnatic violin and vocal separation.

3.2.2 Violin Data Augmentation

This augmentation addresses the instrumentation- and genre-specific MSS challenges in Carnatic music, particularly the *gāyaki* violin style (see Sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.1). Baseline models struggle with the strong frequency overlap between vocals and violin in Carnatic recordings, resulting in residual vocals in the violin stem and vice versa. Even after oversampling the violin-containing tracks in the CMC dataset (see Section 3.1.3), the models continue to have difficulty cleanly separating the two sources. This is exacerbated by the fact that CMC features only a single violinist, recorded in one session under identical conditions.

To improve generalization in Carnatic violin separation, I introduce a **violin data augmentation** that adds more varied violin material to the training set. The augmentation is applied during training with a probability of $p = 0.4$. If the current sample does not already contain a violin, a random 11-second segment from the Bach Violin Dataset (See section 2.6.5) is selected and added to the *other* stem of

the mixture. In MUSDB18 samples, this *other* stem may already contain silence, a melodic instrument, or a synthesizer. For CMC, it either contains tanpura or violin. If the sample already contains violin, the augmentation is skipped to avoid altering the real Carnatic violin-vocal pairs with strong melodic correlation.

The violin augmentation is applied first before other augmentations in the pipeline so that the newly added violin can also be modified by the *scale*, *flip*, and *bleeding augmentations*.

3.2.3 Bleeding Augmentations

The instrumentation- and genre-specific characteristics of the Carnatic domain are addressed through dataset curation (Section 3.1.3) and the violin augmentation (Section 3.2.2). However, the model still only encounters clean, studio-recorded data during training, which does not reflect the live-performed nature of Carnatic music. Real Carnatic recordings rarely have the room-reverb-free quality of the CMC multistem samples. Furthermore, mitigating microphone bleed in the Saraga dataset remains a primary objective of this work (See Section 1.2.2). To better prepare the model for separating Saraga stems containing both the primary source and leaked signals, I implement a simulated bleeding augmentation.

As described in Section 2.2, a microphone m recording source k captures the direct signal $s_m(k)$, convolved with the acoustic path h_{mn} , as well as leakage $u_m(k)$ from other sources:

$$u_m(k) = \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ i \neq m}}^M s_i(k) * h_{mi}(k),$$

where $h_{mi}(k)$ represents the FIR filter describing the acoustic path between the source and microphone. $h_{mi}(k)$ can be modeled with different techniques - as described in Section 2.2.1 by applying filter and gain reduction, following the *SDX challenge* data generation, or via FIR filters, as described in the Section 2.2.

The SDX approach remains an approximation, as the reverberation of a signal in a real room cannot be fully modelled by the sample-wise operations. Room impulse

responses can capture the acoustic path for individual sources, but accurately modelling bleed for an entire ensemble requires a cohesive set of RIRs-ideally recorded in a realistic stage setup.

Given the success of the approximate leakage simulation in the bleeding estimator training (Section 2.2.1), I adopt a sequential augmentation strategy that combines both the SDX simulation and an impulse-response-based method inspired by the DNS challenge.

SDX Bleeding Simulation Augmentation. The SDX bleeding simulation algorithm (Section 2.2.1) is applied as a PyTorch[30]-based augmentation. The parameters follow the SDX defaults: gain reduction between -7 dB and -12 dB, filter order between 3 and 10, low-pass cutoff between 900 Hz and 9,000 Hz, and band-pass ranges of 200-600 Hz and 8-10 kHz for the low and high cutoffs, respectively. Unlike the original SDX procedure, where a single foreground source is chosen and bleed is simulated for each accompanying source, this augmentation is applied independently to each source with a probability of $p = 0.4$. This exposes the model to both clean and corrupted versions of all sources.

Room Impulse Response Convolution Augmentation. Following the DNS challenge methodology (Section 2.6.6), a **room impulse response convolution augmentation** is applied at the end of the augmentation sequence. With a probability of $p = 0.4$ per source, a random RIR from the DNS dataset is selected, resampled to 44.1 kHz, and convolved with the source signal. The resulting audio is then cropped to the model input length, 11 seconds, before being passed to SCNet. By setting $p = 0.4$ for both augmentations, the model sees reverb free audio, audio augmented by one of the reverb-simulations or a sequence of both augmentations.

3.3 Experimental Setup

3.3.1 Finetuning on CMC

The first experiment fine-tunes the SCNet on the upsampled CMC dataset (Section 3.1.3). Due to the limited amount of violin data, only two tracks - one with violin and one without - are kept in the validation set. Model weights are initialized from the official SCNet implementation². The *normal* configuration (not the *large* variant) is used to meet sustainability constraints.

Batch size is reduced from the original 16 (as in the paper) to 4 due to GPU memory limitations. The learning rate remains 0.0005. Although CMC stems are mono, SCNet processes stereo audio. The model is trained with the Adam optimizer ($\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$) and minimizes the *complex spectrogram RMSE* loss (Section 2.5.2). The *Bass* ground truth is set to silence but still included in the loss computation. This configuration is referred to as *SCNet_c*.

3.3.2 Finetuning on CMC plus MUSDB18

The second configuration, *SCNet_{c,m}*, extends the training data by combining CMC with the original pre-training set, MUSDB18. The upsampling strategy described in Section 3.1.3 is applied to CMC. The loss function remains the *complex spectrogram RMSE*, except that the *Bass* ground truths in MUSDB18 are set to silence. This avoids mapping low-frequency components of Carnatic instruments (e.g. *Thom* strokes on the bass membrane of the *mridangam*; see Section 1.2.3) into the bass stem, which in MUSDB18 contains basslines.

3.3.3 Finetuning on CMC plus MUSDB18 with Violin Augmentation

The third configuration, *SCNet_{c,m,v}*, extends *SCNet_{c,m}* with the violin augmentation described in Section 3.2.2, applied at every training step. Figure 9 illustrates the

²<https://github.com/starrytong/SCNet>

Figure 9: Data augmentation pipeline for the $\text{SCNet}_{c,m,v}$ experiment.

augmentation pipeline. The augmentation is applied to the multistem sample

$$x_{\text{sources}} \in \mathbb{R}^{b,s,c,n},$$

where $b = \text{batch size} = 4$, $s = \text{sources} = 4$, $c = \text{channels} = 2$, and $n = \text{samples} = 11 \times 44100 = 485,100$, if the sample does not already contain violin from CMC in the *other* stem. After violin augmentation, the SCNet augmentations *Scale* and *Flip* are applied sequentially with probabilities $p = 0.3$. Finally, the stems are summed to form the mixture

$$x_{\text{mix}} \in \mathbb{R}^{b,1,c,n}$$

that is passed to SCNet.

3.3.4 Finetuning on CMC plus MUSDB18 with Violin and Bleeding Augmentations

The final configuration, $\text{SCNet}_{c,m,v,b}$, adds the bleeding augmentation (Section 2.2.1) to the $\text{SCNet}_{c,m,v}$ pipeline. This augmentation is applied after *Scale* and before RIR augmentation, as shown in Figure 10.

All experiments are run on a single 40 GB GPU for up to 50 epochs, with training monitored and evaluated during runtime. If the separation quality decreases for

Figure 10: Data augmentation pipeline for the $\text{SCNet}_{c,m,v,b}$ experiment.

more than 5 epochs, training is stopped early. After training, the best checkpoint is selected by evaluating SDR scores on segments from the Sanidha and CMC test sets. This checkpoint is then used as the representative model for each configuration.

3.4 Evaluation

As described in Section 3.1.3, two Carnatic test sets are used. Sanidha concerts 2 and 3 serve as the primary benchmark, with a total length of 36:20 minutes. In addition, I evaluate on a second testset, consisting of one track of the CMC dataset, not seen in any training. Saraga, as a more representative dataset for live-recorded Carnatic music (see 2.6.1), is used for the perceptual evaluation.

3.4.1 SDR

The **signal-to-distortion ratio** (SDR) [53] is used for quantitative, data-driven evaluation. SDR measures the loudness ratio between the desired signal and any unwanted distortion, interference, or artifacts in the source - the higher the value, the better the quality.

3.4.2 Perceptual Evaluation

Given the often subtle perceptual differences between the evaluated separation systems, an *expert-based* evaluation was conducted in place of a large-scale listening test.

For each source type (*vocals*, *mridangam*, *violin + tanpura*), 100 five-second excerpts were randomly selected from the Saraga-AV dataset. The *mridangam left* and *mridangam right* stems are summed before separation. Only the meaningful output of the models - *drum* separation for the mridangam sum, *other* separation for violin and *vocals* for singing voice are evaluated.

Two pairwise comparisons were performed:

1. SCNet_{c,m,v} vs. SCNet_{c,m,v,b}, to assess whether the proposed bleeding augmentation improves generalization to mixtures containing source bleed.
2. The strongest proposed model vs. the strongest baseline, HTDemucs_{ft}.

For each excerpt, the expert evaluates the following criteria:

1. **Cleanliness:** For both separations, indicate whether the output is *clean* or contains residual interference from other sources and/or perceptible artifacts.
2. **Preservation:** For both separations, indicate whether the source is *preserved* or *corrupted* (corrupted = missing frequency components of the target source).
3. **Overall Quality:** Select the separation with the highest overall perceptual quality, considering both artifact level and corruption. If both outputs are indistinguishable or of perfect quality, mark as *same*.

3.4.3 Baselines

Four state-of-the-art models are selected as benchmarks, representing some of the best-performing open-source MSS systems available.

	Experiment	Training Data	Finetuning Data
Baselines	HDemucs _{mmi}	MUSDB	800 songs
	HTDemucs	MUSDB	-
	HTDemucs _{ft}	MUSDB + 800 songs	MUSDB + 800 songs
	SCNet	MUSDB	-
Proposed	SCNet _c	MUSDB	CMC
	SCNet _{c,m}	MUSDB	MUSDB, CMC
	SCNet _{c,m,v}	MUSDB	MUSDB, CMC Violin augment
	SCNet _{c,m,v,b}	MUSDB	MUSDB, CMC Violin augment Bleeding augment

Table 3: List of baselines and proposed models with their training and fine-tuning datasets.

- **Fine-tuned Hybrid Transformer Demucs** ($HTDemucs_{ft}$, see Section 2.5.1) - included as the strongest baseline for Carnatic music. This model is trained on MUSDB18 plus 800 additional songs and averages the outputs of four different Hybrid-Demucs models during inference to maximize performance. Two additional Demucs configurations are also included:
- **Hybrid Demucs mmi** ($HDemucs_{mmi}$) - the preceding Demucs generation, which achieved state-of-the-art separation quality at the time of release. It is trained on MUSDB18 plus 800 additional songs and is included here due to its exceptional *mridangam* separation quality.
- **Hybrid Transformer Demucs** ($HTDemucs$) - trained solely on MUSDB18, included for comparison with the fine-tuned variant.
- **Not-fine-tuned SCNet** ($SCNet$ see Section 2.5.2) - serves both as a baseline and as a direct point of comparison to evaluate the impact of fine-tuning. This configuration is trained exclusively on MUSDB18.

Table 3.4.2 gives an overview on the training and finetuning dataset configurations of all baselines and proposed experiments.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Improving the MSS quality for carnatic music

The best checkpoint from each experiment is evaluated on the Sanidha and CMC benchmarks (see Section 3.4) and compared with the baselines (Section 3.4.3). Table 4.1 reports the complete SDR evaluation across all models for the Sanidha benchmark, Table A for the CMC testset. Audio samples are also provided for comparative listening¹.

4.1.1 SDR Evaluation

Overall, all four proposed models outperform all baselines across all three sources and on both test sets. Compared to the SCNet trained solely on MUSDB18, fine-tuning yields substantial improvements - up to +5.4 dB for *vocals*, +6.9 dB for *violin + tanpura*), and +5.5 dB for the *mridangam* source on the Sanidha benchmark. In particular, performance on the *other* stem (*violin+tanpura*) is noteworthy, with SDR values reaching nearly three times those of the best baseline model.

The CMC evaluation delivers similar results - only the *violin+tanpura* source is more than 3db higher than the Sanidha evaluation, suggesting that the model might overfit on the CMC violin. It should be noted that the CMC benchmark contains

¹Google Drive link with evaluation files

Group	Experiment	Vocal	Violin+Tanpura	Mridangam
Baselines	HDemucs _{mmi}	11.86	3.13	<u>10.07</u>
	HTDemucs	12.27	3.52	9.74
	HTDemucs _{ft}	<u>12.63</u>	<u>3.92</u>	8.65
	SCNet	12.59	2.66	8.64
Proposed	SCNet _c	14.76	7.13	13.77
	SCNet _{c,m}	16.67	8.08	13.06
	SCNet _{c,m,v}	18.02	9.65	14.16
	SCNet _{c,m,v,b}	16.30	8.52	14.18

Table 4: Signal-to-Distortion Ratio (dB) on the **Sanidha** benchmark. underline: strongest baseline, **bold**: strongest overall.

only one song, performed by an ensemble that the proposed models encountered during training.

4.1.2 On the Effectiveness of the Proposed Data Augmentations

Violin Augmentation

The $SCNet_{c,m,v}$ configuration achieves the highest overall performance, exceeding the SDR of any other model by more than +1 dB for all sources except *drums*. A direct comparison with $SCNet_{c,m}$ - trained without the violin augmentation - demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed *violin augmentation*. Figure 17 illustrates the impact. Both *vocals*, *violin + tanpura* and *mridangam* show substantial SDR gains compared to the preceding experiment, confirming the augmentation’s value for addressing the strong vocal-violin overlap in Carnatic music.

Bleeding Augmentation

In contrast, the *bleeding augmentation* applied in the $SCNet_{c,m,v,b}$ experiment slightly reduces SDR across all sources except *drums*. For drums, the improvement over $SCNet_{c,m,v}$ is marginal at +0.02 dB - well within the range of measurement noise and thus not statistically meaningful.

Figure 11: Impact of the violin augmentation on the SDR evaluation on Sanidha dataset.

Yet, a perceptual comparison between the models with bleeding augmentation and without, as described in Chapter 3.4.2, show the improved generalization capacities regarding the carnatic violin due to the bleeding augmentation. Figure 12 shows that the $SCNet_{c,m,v,b}$ yielded perceptually better separations in 42% and worse in only 18% of the samples. The bleeding augmentation led to 16% less artifacts/inference-containing samples and 10% less corrupted separations (See Figure 18). Yet, the perceptual quality decreased significantly for mridangam and vocal due to the increase of residuals of other sources in the separations.

4.2 Perceptual Evaluation: $SCNet_{c,m,v}$ vs $HTDemucs_{ft}$

A second perceptual test, as described in Section 3.4.2, is conducted to evaluate whether the best proposed method, $SCNet_{c,m,v}$, (1) generalizes to more realistic, non-studio-recorded data, and (2) whether perceptual quality correlates with the SDR measurement. The overall perceptual quality comparison with the strongest baseline, $HTDemucs_{ft}$, over 100 random Saraga AV samples is shown in Figure 15. Only 13% of the Demucs separations exhibit higher perceptual quality, while 27%

Figure 12: Impact of the bleeding augmentation on perceptual separation quality, computed on Saraga AV.

show no perceivable difference. In 60% of the cases, the proposed method is rated as sounding perceivable better than the strongest baseline.

Figure 13 compares the cleanliness and preservation quality between the two models. The proposed model removes substantially fewer frequencies than the baseline. Only 2% of the vocal separations and 4% of the mridangam samples are corrupted by SCNet_{c,m,v}. The violin corruption rate is higher, at 26%, yet still significantly lower than the baseline’s 54%.

4.2.1 Mridangam Separation

The *mridangam* emerges as the perceptually cleanest separated source. The best proposed model improves SDR by +4.11 dB over the strongest baseline (HDemucs_{mmi}). Figure 14 illustrates how the proposed model preserves significantly more harmonic content (visible as horizontal lines in the spectrogram) from the resonant, tonal strokes - an area where all baselines struggled (compare Figure 7). Perceptually, SCNet_{c,m,v} sounds almost as rich as the original source on nearly all test samples - there is as good as no source corruption (see Figure 13).

The compared baseline, HTDemucs_{ft}, produces cleaner separations - 73% contain no perceivable instrument residuals or artifacts, compared to 61% for the proposed

Saraga Perceptual Evaluation: Cleanliness and preservation quality
Strongest proposed model vs strongest baseline

Figure 13: Amount of samples without artifacts/residuals and without corruption per source of $HTDemucs_{ft}$ and $SCNet_{c,m,v}$.

model. However, this cleanliness is largely due to the heavy gating of the Demucs model, which results in separations containing only transient sounds. In contrast, the proposed model’s separations preserve the harmonic decays of the *mridangam*, although some resonant transients still contain residuals from string instruments or, more rarely, vocals performed at the same pitch as the drum. Overall, the proposed model is rated higher than the strongest baseline in 92% of the *mridangam* samples in the perceptual test (see Figure 15).

4.2.2 Vocal Separation

In contrast to the *mridangam*, the vocal stem is generally well preserved by the strongest baseline, $HTDemucs_{ft}$ (see Figure 13). The observed SDR improvement of +5.39 dB for $SCNet_{c,m,v}$ is primarily due to better removal of interfering sources,

Figure 14: Comparison of spectrograms: *Mridangam* audio separated from Sanidha concert 2 with the pretrained *SCNet* vs the finetuned *SCNet*_{*c,m,v*}. The finetuned preserves the harmonics while the pretrained mainly preserves transients. Compare with Figure 7 for the reference and *HTDemucs*_{*ft*} separations.

particularly the violin. Separation outputs from *SCNet*_{*c,m,v*} contain significantly fewer violin residuals than those from the baselines. While 68% of the samples in the perceptual test contain instrument residuals and artifacts, these are considerably quieter than in the baseline, resulting in an overall substantially higher perceptual quality (see Figure 15).

4.2.3 Violin and Tanpura Separation

The *other* stem, consisting of violin and *tanpura*, shows the largest relative improvement over the baselines. This is particularly important given the strong melodic correlation between violin and vocals in Carnatic music. The violin augmentation appears to play a key role here, as *SCNet*_{*c,m,v*} achieves the highest SDR on both benchmarks for this stem.

Perceptually, the violin and tanpura stem remains the weakest source of the proposed model on the Saraga dataset: frequency components are removed in 26% of the samples, and 61% contain artifacts and/or residuals. Loud, slightly distorted violin sounds in the Saraga dataset are sometimes not correctly identified by the proposed model. Nevertheless, even for this source, the perceptual test shows a significant

Saraga Perceptual Evaluation: Overall perceptual quality
Best proposed model vs best baseline

Figure 15: Perceptual evaluation: Overall best separation quality on Saraga AV.

improvement in overall separation quality relative to the strongest baseline (see Figure 15).

4.3 Training Stability: Extending vs Replacing the Fine-tuning Dataset

Similar work on MSS domain adaptation has highlighted the advantages of fine-tuning pre-trained models, even when pre-training is on out-of-domain data (Section 2.4). This work further suggests that including the out-of-domain dataset in the fine-tuning process can be beneficial.

Figure 16 compares SDR curves on a subset of Sanidha for SCNet_c (CMC only) and $\text{SCNet}_{c,m}$ (CMC + MUSDB18). Including the pretraining dataset MUSDB18 enables longer, more stable fine-tuning and yields higher SDR results. The SDR values in this figure differ from Table 4.1 because only a subset of the Sanidha benchmark is used.

There are several possible explanations for this behaviour. Training exclusively on CMC may lead to overfitting, given its smaller size and limited variability. The hyperparameters (e.g., learning rate) may not be optimally tuned for CMC. Furthermore, the SCNet checkpoints provided by the authors have been extensively trained on MUSDB18; removing this data from fine-tuning might destabilize training by moving the model too far from its pre-trained distribution.

Figure 16: SDR development per fine-tuning epoch and source on a subset of the Sanidha benchmark. SCNet_c shows a rapid quality boost after the first epoch followed by a decline. SCNet_{c,m} declines only after 25 epochs.

Chapter 5

Conclusion and Discussion

This work improves source separation quality for Carnatic music. The data-driven evaluation shows significant improvements on the Sanidha dataset for all three sources over the best available benchmarks. The perceptual study confirms these gains, as the proposed model outperforms the baseline HTDemucs_{ft} on the live-recorded Saraga dataset for all three stems. In particular, the mridangam separations achieve substantial perceptual improvements, with the proposed model removing significantly fewer harmonics.

The violin augmentation demonstrates that sampling semi-out-of-domain data - such as unsynchronized Western classical violin instead of Carnatic violin - can be an effective approach in domain adaptation problems. Furthermore, this work shows that including an out-of-domain pretraining dataset, such as MUSDB18, into the fine-tuning stage can lead to increased training stability and quality improvements for the Carnatic music domain.

The proposed bleeding augmentation requires further investigation to be effectively applied in recording-situation domain adaptation tasks. While the augmentation led to slightly better *mridangam* performance and produced some perceptually improved separations for the *violin + tanpura* track, the experiment without this augmentation still performed significantly better on two of the sources from the live-recorded Carnatic dataset Saraga, despite only being trained on studio recordings.

Another limitation of this work is the grouping of tanpura and violin into a single stem. This decision was based on how these sources are grouped in the separations of pre-trained MSS systems (see Section 3.1.1). From a musicological perspective, this grouping is questionable: the violin and tanpura differ greatly in timbre and serve distinct roles in Carnatic performance - the violin follows the vocalist, while the *tanpura* provides a continuous drone (see Section 1.2.3). A possible extension of this work would be to separate these instruments into distinct stereo channels within SCNet, while retaining the fine-tuning strategy presented here.

Perceptual tests also show that baselines such as HTDemucs_{ft} still produce cleaner-sounding separations for certain samples. The proposed models often contain subtle background artifacts and residuals - not loud enough to heavily impact quantitative metrics, but still perceptible. It is likely that some advantages of large pre-trained models arise from extensive experience in AI training, greater financial and computational resources, and careful selection of the optimal final checkpoint. These issues can be addressed in future work to enable truly clean, artifact-free carnatic source separation.

The models trained in this work are released via compIAM¹.

¹<https://github.com/MTG/compIAM>

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Appendix A

Appendix

Group	Experiment	Vocal	Violin+Tanpura	Mridangam
Baselines	HDemucs _{mmi}	8.63	2.92	<u>8.64</u>
	HTDemucs	8.98	3.17	7.71
	HTDemucs _{ft}	<u>9.89</u>	<u>4.06</u>	7.66
	SCNet	9.38	2.70	4.18
Proposed	SCNet _c	12.93	7.97	10.37
	SCNet _{c,m}	15.68	10.46	13.04
	SCNet _{c,m,v}	17.74	12.76	13.65
	SCNet _{c,m,v,b}	15.95	10.76	12.60

Table 5: Signal-to-Distortion Ratio (dB) on the **CMC** benchmark. underline: strongest baseline, **bold**: strongest overall. The CMC benchmark only contains one track, not seen during training. Yet, the results are comparable to the Sanidha benchmark, see Figure 4.1.

Figure 17: Impact of the bleeding augmentation on the SDR evaluation, computed for the Sanidha benchmark.

Saraga Perceptual Evaluation: Cleanliness and preservation quality
With vs without bleeding augmentation

Figure 18: Impact of the bleeding augmentation on perceptual separation quality, computed on Saraga AV. Compared is the amount of samples without artifacts/residuals and without corruption per source